

IDENTIFYING MOTIVATION FOR SHEA NUTS GATHERING IN AN URBAN COMMUNITY FROM GHANA

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Abstract

Fruit bats survey and interviews were conducted to collect data on bat roosting sites and gatherers' motivation for collecting nuts respectively. Three different fruit bat species were identified from four different roosting sites. Income was identified to be the major motivating factor among the five factors that urged the gatherers to collect Shea nuts. Gatherers mentioned more often that bat discarded nuts have short shelf life than any other demotivating factor. There was a statistically significant relationship between demotivating factors and gatherers' discriminatory tendencies against bat discarded nuts ($X^2=31.536$, $Df=5$, $P=7.342e-6$). However, there was no statistically significant relationship between demotivating and motivating factors ($X^2= 26.592$, $Df=20$, $P=0.1471$).

Gatherers without formal education made the largest sales from Shea nuts than the educated. There was statistically significant relationship between educational background and income generated from Shea nuts ($X^2= 47.303$, $Df=27$, $P= 9.175e-3$). The widowed had the highest median income values from Shea nuts although there was no statistically significant relationship between marital status and income generated. All age groups were involved in Shea nuts gathering and the general trend suggested the levels of incomes generated increase with age. There was a statistically significant relationship between gatherers' age and number of children whereas there was no statistically significant relationship between the number of children and income generated.

Key words: demotivation, fruit bat, gathering, motivation, roosting, Shea nuts

INTRODUCTION

Gathering of natural resources for subsistence is not only rooted in the past but still part of rural livelihoods especially those in the developing world (Blench, 2001; Getzner, Islam, 2013; Laube, 2015; Nawrotzki et al., 2012; Moore, 2008). Really, gathering of some natural resources in some instances has served as a raw material base for the manufacture of modern products. Nuts from the Shea tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) are one such natural resource that are gathered across the Savanna regions of Africa for its essential economic and other benefits.

Blench, 2001 reported how the Shea trade has lasted for more than millennia across the 18 African countries where the species thrives in the Savanna. The Shea tree has economic, socio-cultural and ecological relevance and these functions have molded the landscape of the people who utilise it (Fontaine et al., 2004). Products derived from the Shea tree span across cosmetics to foods directly prepared from its fruits or as an added supplement. The species medicinal properties come from the leaves, the

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bark and the nuts. For example, the butter from the nuts has healing properties for treating diseases like eczema, sunburns, wounds and fractures (Laube, 2015).

Shea nut is processed into butter either to be used at home or sold at the local markets. However, in most cases kernels are sold at the local markets or to large scale processors for industrial production of butter. The literature has reported how remarkably the Shea trade is solely done by women (Rammohan, 2010). The impression from literature is that the Shea trade serves as a readily income source for the women gatherers in the lean season where little farm work is done. Shea nut processing into butter is tedious. Homemade Shea butter processing begins with fruit collection and shelling off the pulp to the boiling of the nuts. Grinding nuts could either be manual or machine driven. The mashed nuts is then cooked to decant the oil to cool off to get the butter. In all these, the processors' wages do not commensurate with the costs of labour and fuel use in processing the nuts into butter at the subsistence level.

Notwithstanding the Shea tree enormous benefits, there are challenges in realizing its economic potential in Ghana. Some of the challenges are: (1) undefined access rights, (2) transportation difficulties to collection points, (3) inefficient processing methods, (4) inefficient energy sources and (5) difficulties in marketing the products. Access to the Shea tree differs from place to place. For example, in the study area there are no clear rules governing the right of access and thus gatherers can collect nuts from any tree they come across. The right of access is hindered really in urban communities where limited patches of the species stands are available. The limited number of trees in urban communities generate competition for access or simply it wanes the interest in the long held tradition of gathering Shea nuts when it is in season.

The challenges enumerated above could explain the reasons that demotivate people to gather Shea nuts in urban communities. This study assumed that Shea nuts gatherers in an urban community called Tumu in the Upper West Region of Ghana are motivated to collect nuts not only from Shea trees but also nuts discarded by fruit bats. This assumption is appropriate, for the literature points to the notion that collectors develop new strategies to motivate themselves to collect plant resources when conditions change (Schunko et al., 2015).

The purpose of this study was to assess gatherers motivation to collect Shea nuts in an urban community where the commodity is relatively scarce. The objective was to assess if gatherers deliberately add to their collection bat discarded nuts. Thus, increasing bat colonies in the community could be an additional source of Shea nuts and that would also promote bat conservation. The study also aimed to assess demographic factors that

motivate gatherers to increase income generated from gathering Shea nuts in the community.

Four main questions were asked for the study:

1. What species of fruit bats have colonies in the community?
2. What factors motivate gatherers to collect Shea nuts in the community ?
3. How do gatherers motivation and demotivation factors relate in collecting fruit bats discarded nuts ?
4. How do demographic factors of (I) educational background, (II) marital status, (III) age of the gatherer and (IV) number of children motivate gatherers' levels of income generated from Shea nuts ?

Theoretical Perspectives of Gatherers' Motivation

The study was to understand whether the limited access for Shea trees in the urban community motivate the gatherers to include other sources of the nuts into their collection. The theoretical background of this study relates gatherers motivation for collecting Shea nuts under both Shea trees and fruit bats discarded nuts.

The Notion of Motivation

Motivation inspires one to do with a zeal to achieve an end whiles demotivation indicates lack of impetus to perform an activity. There are both internal and external values that motivate or demotivate an individual into performing a task (Bénabou, Tirole, 2003). Motivation is described to have both intrinsic and extrinsic values that span the continuum between 'motivated not to do' to 'motivated to do' (Ryan, Deci, 2000).

Intrinsic motivation promotes inherent tendencies of interest that enjoins one to perform a task. The inherent tendencies of intrinsic motivation is derived from an individual autonomy that enable free choices to be made without being coerced (Singh, 2016). That is individual interests and satisfaction derive from his/her activities are treasured in intrinsic motivation.

Extrinsic motivation however, requires the influences of external values to produce a separable outcome (Ryan, Deci, 2000). Nonetheless, extrinsic motivation can sometimes be inherently induced to promote certain perceived values associated with certain activities and their outcomes. Thus, extrinsic motivation can either be externally driven to avoid sanctions or self-endorsed to gain certain functional values (Yoo et al., 2012).

Shea Nuts Gatherers' Motivation and Fruit Bats Discarded Nuts

Djossa et al., 2008 stated Shea nuts are dispersed mostly by three species of fruit bats found in West Africa. These flying mammals are the The Gambian epauletted fruit bat (*Epomophorus gambianus*), Peters's dwarf epauletted fruit bat (*Micropteropus pusillus*), and Veldkamp's dwarf

epauletted fruit bat (*Nanonycteris veldkampii*). These animals have special pouches in their mouth that can store many nuts which are carried to roosting sites (Kingdon, 1997). The bats eat the fruit pulp and then discard the nuts under their roosting sites.

Shea nuts gatherers could seize the opportunity provided by bats' colonies to augment nuts gathered directly under Shea trees in the community. The advantage is that extra nuts are carried from the feeding grounds of the bats to the community which the women could collect from the roosting sites of the bats. Apart from the gatherers not walking long distances to collect such nuts, it would also reduce the danger of suffering snakebites which is common under Shea trees in the bushes. The Shea fruit is succulent and thus attract rodents and other eaters which leads to snakes laying ambush to prey on the primary consumers.

Rejecting or collecting bat discarded nuts together with those under Shea trees would fit into Yoo et al., 2012 statement that indicated motivation empowers one to reflect and assimilate new ideas to undertake or not to undertake a task. Although Bénabou, Tirole 2003, mentioned intrinsic and extrinsic motivations may sometimes conflict with each other, it would require both components of motivation for gatherers to collect nuts under Shea trees and/or bat discarded nuts.

The above claims could be useful to the gatherers if rallying for such motivation would provide utility outcomes. Moser et al., 2011 stated the quality of a product to consumers is influenced by both its intrinsic and extrinsic evidences provided by the producer/seller of the product. Thus, a combination of opportunities provided by available Shea tree stands and bats roosting sites in the community together with the mind, knowledge, power and skills of the gatherers would be needed to provide motivation for collecting nuts (Assche et al., 2017; Poudel, 2012; Timiș-Gânsac et al., 2018).

In this context, the gatherers have been assumed to be motivated to collect nuts from both traditionally known source (under Shea trees) and other sources (bat discarded nuts) with the new conditions of relatively nuts scarcity in the community. Food, medicine, income, tradition and recreation have been stated as the major motivational factors that encourage people to gather plant resources from the wild. These motivational factors hinge on the needs of the people especially in subsistence situations as pertain in the study area.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study Area. Tumu is the district capital of the Sissila East Municipality. The 2010 population and housing census had the town's population as 11,086 as against the total municipal population of 56,528.

Agricultural activities form the major occupation of the people with 84.4 % of the working population. However, there are considerable differences in the economic activities depending on the location. According to the Ghana Statistical Service, 2010, the majority of households (94.9 %) in the rural areas were engaged in agriculture as against 56.9 % for the urban dwellers in the municipality.

There are parklands of Shea trees and assemblage of either planted or natural tree stands of different tree species that have canopies for bat roosting in the town. The dominant tree species that provide bat roosting niches are the neem (*Azadirachta indica*), mahogany (*Khaya senegalensis*) and stands of mangoes (*Mangifera indica*) in the town.

Data collection. Data collection was structured into two sections. The first was to locate clusters of tree stands where fruit bats roost. It was to identify the bat species, estimate their populations as well as the tree species they roost. The second section was to locate women who collect Shea nuts in the community for interviews. Data collection took place in the fruiting season of the Shea tree in the community (beginning 1st June to the 31st August, 2019).

Marking Bat Roosting Sites. A snowballing technique was used to identify roosting sites of fruit bats in the community through key informant approach (Wilcke, 2006). A global position system (GPS) coordinates were taken at the estimated center of each roosting site identified. Four research assistants counted the number of individual bats on a roosting site simultaneously. Counting was done in mid-afternoon (between 12 noon and 1Pm) where bats are mostly docile (Hayman et al., 2012). Care was taken not to arouse the bats while counting was going on to allow for sequential counting of all individuals sighted. The figures obtained by each counter was added and the averages calculated to represent the number of individual bats for each site. The species were then identified with the help of field guide.

All Shea nuts seen under each roosting site were collected for three consecutive days during the peak period in July. The nuts were counted to get an idea of possible number of nuts that are carried from feeding grounds by bats. The average number of nuts counted is presented at the results section.

Interviews. A semi structured interview guide was used to collect data on motivating factors for collecting nuts and demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts. The interview questions included incomes generated from Shea nuts and gatherers' demography. Focus group discussion was conducted after interviews were completed to clarify issues.

The community was divided into four units at the central point (the Post Office area). Clusters of Shea tree stands and bat roosting sites in each

unit was earmarked as points to find gatherers for interview. A Shea nut tree clusters in this study is defined to be within human settlement in the community. The earmarked clusters had at least thirty Shea trees with the average breast height girth of 30cm. Nine clusters were identified with two each located in each unit except one unit which had three clusters. The researchers tested the interview guide with five gatherers sampled accidentally at nuts collection points. After correcting errors detected during the test run, one research assistant was assigned to each of the four units to look for gatherers to interview.

The four research assistants visited their assigned clusters between 6 am and 9 am and between 4pm and 6pm weekly to get respondents for interviews. Snowballing sampling technique was also used to locate other gatherers who picked Shea nuts in the community. Each cluster was visited until no new gatherer was identified. No gatherer was interviewed twice but their phone contacts and house numbers were taken. The researchers followed on each respondent weekly to collect the quantity of nuts that had been gathered or sold.

The research assistants would move to the next cluster of Shea trees within their units if there were no gatherers at the time of visit or when interviews were completed in a cluster. Gatherers were asked for their consent before interviews were conducted. Children (girls) who gathered nuts for their mothers were followed to their homes to interview their mothers. Interviews lasted between 15 minutes and 20 minutes. Each research assistant submitted data gathered weekly to the main researchers. This allowed for editing and cleaning of the data on regular basis.

Focus Group Discussion. A focus group discussion was conducted after the nut collection season to clarify issues identified during the interview sessions (Creswell, 1998). Selection of participants was based on representation from each of the four units and also the quantity that a gatherer collected. The three highest gatherers in each unit were selected for the focus group discussion bringing the total to 12. The views expressed by participants enhanced the interview data gathered for analysis.

Data Analysis. Data were analysed with the help of the statistical software-Statistics-open-for-all (SOFA) (Self, 2017). Data have been analysed and presented in descriptive and inferential statistics format. Chi Square statistics was mainly used because data was grouped at the nominal level. The results are presented in tables and charts. Gatherers' incomes were derived from the quantity of Shea nuts gathered after the season and the local market value of a kilogram for the nuts in 2019.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results presentation begins with fruit bats survey conducted in the community on 2nd June, 2019 after a reconnaissance survey was undertaken on the previous day to locate roosting sites. The subsequent sections present the results from interview and focus group discussions data.

Location of Fruit Bats Colonies in Tumu. Four fruit bat colonies were identified in the community. The general observation was that the preference sites for roosting were on tall trees (above 7 meters) with open canopy vegetation. Hayman et al., 2012 made similar findings for Straw Coloured bat roosting preferences. Table 1 below provides detail description of the identified bat colonies.

Table 1

Identified Bats and Roosting Sites Description in Tumu

Location Description	GPS Coordinates	Identified Bat Species	Average Counts of bats	Roosting Tree Species/ number of nuts counted
Place serves as playground for Draught and <i>Oware</i> games. Nine lottery vendor kiosks and a food joint are located in the area. There is no undergrowth.	10. 877 45 N; 001.984 10 W	Dwarf Epauletted Fruit Bat (<i>Micropteropus pusillus</i>) (Kingdon, 1997).	363	Neem (9 trees) <i>Azadirachta indica</i> Average nuts counted=438
In front of the Tumu College of Education Administration Block with no undergrowth.	10.891 87 N; 001.985 59 W	Epauletted Fruit Bat (<i>Epauletted gambianus</i>) (Kingdon, 1997).	70	Mango (18 trees) <i>Mangifera indica</i> Average nuts counted=123
An alley of mango trees leading to staff quarters of the Tumu College of Education with little undergrowth.	10.893 41 N; 001.985 33 W	Epauletted Fruit Bat (<i>Epauletted gambianus</i>) (Kingdon, 1997).	122	Mango (18 trees) <i>Mangifera indica</i> Average nuts counted =243
Located on the Campus of the Kanton Senior High School. Their stay was temporal for less than two months. This species is known to be migratory (Hayman et al., 2012).	10.873218N 001.978953W	Straw Coloured Fruit Bat (<i>Eidolon helvum</i>) (Kingdom, 1997).	432	Mahogany (7 trees) <i>Khaya senegalensis</i> Average nuts counted = 652

The findings in this study showed mostly, majority of the roosting orientation was towards the leeward side of the trees that pointed towards the western ends of the tree canopies. This finding indicates the bats roosting orientation preferences was to reduce the negative impacts of the early to midday heat and to enjoy sunset low temperatures before flying to feeding sites. This agrees with Ruczynski et al., 2007 report that indicated the level of temperature is a factor in bat roosting preferences. The authors stated high temperatures affect bat thermoregulation activities negatively.

Gatherers' Motivating Factors. All the 81 Shea nuts gatherers identified were interviewed. Respondents were asked to mention one major motivational factor for collecting Shea nuts. The gatherers' motivational factors were grouped into income, food, medicine, tradition and recreation.

Below are the details of the percentage coverage of each motivational factor that urged the gatherers to collect Shea nuts in the community (Fig. 1).

The proportions of income and food constituted more than half of the factors that motivated gatherers to collect Shea nuts in the community. With the exception of tradition and recreation which can be standalone motivational factors, the other three are linked. This was evident during the focus group discussion, it came out that those who mentioned food or medicine did not necessarily used the nuts solely for those purposes but rather the nuts were sold to purchase those items. Laube, 2015 and Moore, 2008 made similar findings where incomes generated from Shea nuts were spent on household items like medicine, soap and was also use to improve household food security. It can be said primarily, much as these motivating factors (particularly tradition and recreation) were intrinsically generated, the interest for getting satisfaction from Shea nuts income was inspired by extrinsically separable outcomes of using the money to buy basic needs.

Fig. 1. Gatherers' Motivation for Collecting Shea nuts

Demotivating Factors and Discriminatory Tendencies against Bat Discarded Nuts. Respondents were asked whether they discriminate by gathering only from under Shea trees or they deliberately add bat discarded nuts from their roosting sites. Sixty nine (85.19 %) said they discriminate against gathering bat discarded nuts. Gatherers were asked again to name their major demotivating factor against bat discarded nuts. The results were: Short shelf life (42), do not attract good price (7), uncertainty about the source (6), light in weight (6), do not produce enough oil (9) and could be contaminated (11).

These demotivating factors could negatively affect the Shea nut value chain because they all have adverse impacts on the market value of nuts sold and therefore the level of income that can be generated. For example, Esiegbuya et al., 2014 pointed out healthy Shea nuts have brownish-creamy colour which loses out to blackish and whitish colours when infested with certain fungi strains. The fungi infestation could be what the gatherers alluded to about bat discarded nuts darkening fast and therefore do not attract good price. Obviously, these demotivating factors would not promote a competitive value chain for bat discarded nuts.

Gatherers’ demotivating factors and discriminatory tendencies relationship. A statistical question was asked to determine the relationship between demotivating factors and discriminatory tendencies of the gatherers against bat discarded nuts. Below is the details of a Chi Square test of association between demotivating factors and gatherers’ discriminatory tendencies against bat discarded nuts (Table 2).

Table 2

Demotivating factors and Discriminatory Patterns of Gatherers against Bat Discarded Nuts

		Do You Discriminate Against Bat Discarded Nuts ?					
		Yes		No		TOTAL	
		Obs.	Exp.	Obs.	Exp.	Obs.	Exp.
Demotivating Factors Against Bats' Discarded Nuts	Short Shelf Life (germinates, darkens)	41	35.8	1	6.2	42	42
	Do not attract Good Price	6	6.0	1	1.0	7	7
	Uncertainty about Source	6	5.1	0	0.9	6	6
	Light in Weight	3	5.1	3	0.9	6	6
	Do not have enough Oil	3	7.7	6	1.3	9	9
	Could be Contaminated	10	9.4	1	1.6	11	11
	TOTAL	69	69	12	12	81	81

$$X^2 = 31.536, Df = 5, P = 7.342e-6$$

The results showed there was a statistically significant relationship $X^2 = 31.536, Df=5, P=7.342e-6$ between the two variables at 1 %. Although 14.81 % of the gatherers said they did not discriminate against bat discarded nuts, they still had demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts. For example, three and six of the gatherers who did not discriminate believed bat discarded nuts were light in weight and do not yield enough oil respectively. The gatherers who do not discriminate against bat discarded nuts said although they do discriminate, they do not also deliberately search for them but would add them to their collection when they come across.

Although gatherers’ demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts could be debated, Djossa et al., 2008 findings support some of their assertions. For example, the researchers mentioned bats normally choose seeds that are smaller in size but with a good pulp to enable them carry the

nuts for longer distances to roosting sites. In reference to the above, the gatherers would be right to state bat discarded nuts are light in weight and rightly yield less oil. Again, most often gatherers who produce homemade Shea butters do not readily process nuts gathered for oil, but rather store them until after the farming season. Findings confirmed bat discarded nuts germination successes improve more than non-bat processed nuts and this supports the gatherers' claims that bat discarded nuts germinate quickly.

Ryan, Deci, 2000 mentioned extrinsic motivation could be inherently or externally induced to promote certain perceived values associated with certain activities and their outcomes. The authors' statement is reflected in the demotivating factors of the gatherers. It could be stated for example, the gatherers applied an inherently self-endorsed extrinsic motivation on demotivating factors of "uncertainty about the source" and "could be contaminated" against bat discarded nuts to gain some sentimental values. Again, it could be said the rest of the demotivating factors were externally induced to avoid losing certain utility values. Actually, the externally induced extrinsic motivation formed the majority of the demotivating factors.

It stands to reason that the gatherers have certain knowledge, skill, mind and power about Shea nuts value chain that informed their demotivation against bat discarded nuts. The above assertion relates to Moser et al., 2011, statement that indicated every product's intrinsic and extrinsic values are what is portrayed by the producer or the seller to attract buyers. Thus, it is not surprising that the gatherers exhibited these demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts which obviously they believed will negatively affect the utility outcomes of the nuts they collect - the income.

Motivating and demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts relationship. The study found out there was no statistically significant differences between motivating and demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts ($X^2 = 26.592$, $Df = 20$, $P = 0.1471$) at 5 %. This suggests although demotivating factors such as short shelf life of bat discarded nuts dominated gatherers responses, the general motivating factors for gathering Shea nuts overrode the concerns about the source of the nuts. In other words, most gatherers (85.19 %) did not pay attention to bat discarded nuts but rather concentrated on the traditionally known source-- only under Shea trees.

Details of the Chi Square test between motivating factors for gathering Shea nuts and demotivating factors' relationship against bats' discarded nuts is shown below (Table 3).

Demographic Factors and Motivation for Generating Income from Shea Nuts. The study assessed demographic factors of: (I)

educational background, (II) marital status, (III) age of the gatherer and (IV) number of children relationship with gatherers' motivation for generating income from Shea nuts. An estimated income of each gatherer was conducted based on the number of kilograms of nuts gathered and sold. The assessment was based on the market value of the nuts at the end of the gathering season for 2019. This is exclusive of homemade butter sold or used in the homes because it was difficult to get figures.

Shea nuts are sold in small quantities to middlemen who act as agents for the large scale processors. A measuring can is used to measure the nuts for saleable units and averagely it takes about 30 cans to make a bag load of between 82 kg and 90 kg. The largest sales (656 Kg of eight bags) made by a gatherer in this study amounted to one thousand and two hundred Ghana Cedis (GHS 1,200.00) and the least sale was (82 kg of one bag) amounted to one hundred and fifty Ghana Cedis (GHS 150.00). The monetary values equivalency respectively in United States dollars was two hundred and fifty dollars (\$ 250) and thirty one dollars and twenty five cents (\$ 31.25), (exchange rate at \$1≡ GHS 4.8 at August, 2019).

Table 3

Motivating and Demotivating Factors against Bats' Discarded Nuts Relationship

		Motivation for Collecting Shea Nuts										TOTAL	
		Income		Food		Medicine		Tradition		Recreation			
		Ob.	Ex.	Ob.	Ex.	Ob.	Ex.	Ob.	Ex.	Ob.	Ex.		
Demotivating Factors Against Bats' Discarded Nuts	Short Shelf life (germinates and darkens fast)	6	13.0	15	10.9	9	6.2	5	6.2	7	5.7	42	42
	Will not attract Good price	4	2.2	1	1.8	0	1.0	1	1.0	1	1.0	7	7
	Uncertainty about Source	3	1.9	1	1.6	1	0.9	0	0.9	1	0.8	6	6
	Light in Weight	2	1.9	1	1.6	2	0.9	1	0.9	0	0.8	6	6
	Do not yield enough oil	4	2.8	2	2.3	0	1.3	1	1.3	2	1.2	9	9
	Could be contaminated	6	3.4	1	2.9	0	1.6	4	1.6	0	1.5	11	11
	TOTAL	25	25	21	21	12	12	12	12	11	11	81	81

$$X^2 = 26.592, Df = 20, P = 0.1471$$

Educational level and income generation relationship. Figure 2 clearly indicates that those with no or little formal education generated higher levels of income than those with higher education from Shea nuts. For example, the plot for tertiary education did not show in the figure because there were less than four entries. Although there were income generation disparities within each group, the median values of GHS 900, GHS 600 and GHS 450 recorded for none, Primary/Junior and Senior

Secondary levels respectively showed a general variability among the different groups.

There was a statistically significant relationship between educational background and income generated from Shea nuts in a Chi Square test ($\chi^2 = 47.303$, Df = 27, P = 9.175e-3) at 5 %. The result for the different educational background groups' proportions involve in Shea nuts gathering is not different from previous studies. Laube, 2015 made similar findings where gatherers with no educational background formed the majority at above 70 %.

The argument could be made that those with low levels of education see incomes from Shea nuts not only as stopgap, but rather a venerable income generating source to complement petty trading and farming. These arguments are based on literature that suggest Shea nut gatherers' passion to generate income is to provide complementary sources of earnings derive from diverse livelihood activities. Again, it could be stated those with higher education may have less time to engage in Shea nut gathering because they could be engaged in formal work. Thus, it could be said it is not because of disinterests or the tradition has waned among the educated to gather Shea nuts. For example, Laube, 2015 stated the traditional knowledge of Shea nut processing had not died down among the female population in northern Ghana, except that Shea butter can now easily be purchased at the local markets.

Fig. 2. Income level versus Education level

Marital status and income generation relationship. The median values for incomes generated from Shea nuts based on marital status were from the highest to the lowest: Widowed (GHS 900), followed by the married (GHS 750) and both the unmarried before and the divorced had

their median values at GHS 600. The figures showed variability within and among the different marital status groups (Fig. 3). Even the married, whom it is assumed to have economic support from their husbands had the second highest income levels, this is an indication of how women from the study area are regarded to be the main actors of providing food for their households.

There was no statistically significant relationship between marital status and the level of income generated from Shea nuts in Chi Square test of association $X^2 = 16.094$, $Df = 15$, $P = 0.3758$) at 5 %. The results indicate the motivation for Shea nut gathering goes beyond the gatherers' marital status in society. Shea nut is probably one of the major resources in Ghana that provides some financial independence to the poor rural women in that part of the country. Laube, 2015 for example stated traditionally, women are not allowed to own land in northern Ghana but rely on the benevolence of their husbands to cultivate crops. Therefore generating income from Shea nuts which is used to support households especially during the lean season comes in handy. This is buttressed by the results from this study which showed the widowed were motivated to generate more income than the rests of the groups because they may have little or no other income generating sources as their husbands are no more.

Fig. 3. Income Level versus Marital status

Gatherers' age groups and income generation relationship. The median values for incomes generated from Shea nuts for the different age groups indicated the lowest was for the 21 to 30 age group with GHS 450 to the highest of GHS 975 for the above 60 age group. The general trend showed the level of income generation from Shea nuts increased with

increasing age. Below are the details for gatherers' age and income generation from Shea nuts (Fig. 4).

From Fig. 4, it is rather the elderly that gathered more to generate higher income than the younger gatherers. This finding contrast Carette et al., 2009 report where the elderly rather gathered less than the young. The reason for this contrasting findings could be attributed to the gatherers not walking longer distances to gather Shea nuts in this study, but rather gathering was concentrated in the community. Laube, 2015 assertion that elderly women have greater access and control to Shea trees than the younger counterparts could also be a factor that enabled the elderly to collect more nuts in this study.

There was no statistically significant relationship between gatherers' age group and the level of income generated from Shea nuts in Chi Square test of association ($X^2 = 54.325$, $Df = 45$, $P = 0.1628$) at 5 %. This indicates age is not a barrier to gathering Shea nuts in the community and this confirms Laube, 2015 findings that showed all age groups engage in Shea nuts gathering.

Fig. 4. Income versus Age group

Gatherers' age, income generation and number of children relationship. There was statistically significant relationship between number of children and gatherers' age $X^2 = 54.212$, $Df = 30$, $P = 4.354e-3$ at 5 %. It could be argued that as gatherers aged, they have more children who depend on them for support and that motivate them to generate more income from Shea nuts. It could also mean an older gatherer would have more hands to support to increase nuts gathering.

The least number of children for a gatherer was one and the highest was seven. The income range between the least and the highest number of children a gatherer had was GHS 450 and GHS 825 respectively. That notwithstanding, there was no statistically significant relationship between the number of children and incomes generated from Shea nuts in a Chi Square test of association ($X^2 = 50.212$, Df = 54, P = 0.6213) at 5 %.

CONCLUSIONS

This study applied a survey technique to locate bat roosting sites for identification and census. Three different bat species were identified from four roosting sites in the community. The flying mammals identified were Dwarf Epauletted Fruit Bat (*Micropteropus pusillus*), Epauletted Fruit Bat (*Epauletted gambianus*) and Straw Coloured Fruit Bat (*Eidolon helvum*). Hundreds of peeled Shea nuts carried from feeding grounds by bats were seen under each roosting site.

This study assumed that Shea nuts gatherers in an urban community are motivated to collect nuts not only from Shea trees and that they do not discriminate against nuts discarded by fruit bats. Interviews were conducted to gather data on gatherers' motivating factors for collecting Shea nuts and demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts. The findings showed however, that the majority of the gatherers (85.19 %) discriminate against bat discarded nuts.

Five motivating factors were identified to urge the gatherers to collect Shea nuts in the community. They were income, food, medicine, tradition and recreation. Gatherers responses suggested income was the major motivational factor that urged them to collect nuts.

Six demotivating factors were identified and the major among them was that bat discarded nuts have short shelf life. There was a statistically significant relationship between demotivating factors and gatherers' discriminatory tendencies against bat discarded nuts in Chi Square test. However, there was no statistically significant relationship between demotivating and motivating factors in a Chi Square test mainly because gatherers do not pay particular attention to bat discarded nuts.

The largest sales made from Shea nuts by a gatherer was equivalent to \$250 and the least was \$ 31.25 at the end of the 2019 gathering season. Gatherers with no education made the largest sales from Shea nuts than the educated. There was statistically significant relationship between educational background and income generated from Shea nuts in a Chi Square test. Although there was no statistically significant relationship between marital status and income generated from Shea nuts, the widowed had the highest median values for incomes generated from Shea nuts. These

results indicate Shea nuts is a major resource that provides readily source of income to vulnerable women in northern Ghana.

The findings showed gatherers were made up of all ages with the general trend suggesting the levels of incomes generated increase with age although there was no statistically significant relationship between the two variables. However, there was a statistically significant relationship between gatherers' age and number of children whereas there was no statistically significant relationship between the number of children and income generated from Shea nuts. These results suggest as gatherers aged, they have many children who need to be supported thus, requiring more resources to cater for them or probably more hands would have been developed to support in the gathering enterprise.

The findings of this study indicate Shea nut gatherers had both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for gathering. The gatherers also had both intrinsically and extrinsically inspired demotivation against bat discarded nuts. Income was the major motivating factor for collecting Shea nuts and it was the main reason behind demotivating factors against bat discarded nuts which was to prevent a devaluation of the Shea nuts value chain.

This study was conducted in only one urban community and the number of gatherers sampled were limited. It is therefore recommended that the research be expanded to cover other urban communities in the Shea nuts belt to properly understand gatherers motivation and its relationship with bat discarded nuts which could support bat conservation and Shea nuts dispersal.

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